

LOVE OF THE COUNTRY - A SIGN OF FAITH, PROTECTION AND CONSERVATION OF GREEN SPACE

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Abstract. *This article talks about the reforms in the field of ecology that are being carried out in our country. Normative legal documents, programs and projects aimed at protecting the environment were also cited, and the problem of increasing the environmental culture of the population was analyzed, and a number of proposals for its elimination were reflected.*

Keywords: *ecology, environment, "Green space", ecological control, action strategy, ecological culture.*

INTRODUCTION

As long as there are brave men in the country who love, honor and protect the country, this country will always rise and flourish. For every country, every nation, there is probably no place more honorable than the Motherland where they were born and raised. When Rasulullah (s.a.w.) was emigrating to Medina, he turned to Makkah and said: "If my people had not forced me to leave Makkah, I would not have left Makkah of my own free will." [1]

At the present time, when the whole world is developing and the process of globalization is accelerating, it is necessary to carry out reforms, introduce innovations, and keep up with the times. Taking these into account, reforms and changes are being implemented in every field every day. In addition, in our country, among other areas, we pay serious attention to the issues of ensuring environmental stability, creating the necessary conditions for the population to have a comfortable natural environment, rational and effective use of natural resources, preventing emerging environmental problems and eliminating their negative consequences. attention is being paid.

Improving the documents on ecology and environmental protection, improving the ecological culture of the population and increasing their activity in environmental protection, wide introduction of information and communication technologies in the field, development of the public environmental control system, training of public inspectors and improving their skills, a number of effective works are being carried out to solve waste problems. In developed countries, the necessary legal and regulatory documents are developed and verified in order to reduce the negative impact on the environment. Legal regulations have been implemented in our country in terms of establishing a balance between production and the environment. In our country, awareness about the protection of the natural environment and the minimization of possible negative effects is increasing. [1]

A number of legal documents were adopted this year. Including:

Resolution No. 443 of the Cabinet of Ministers of August 10, 2022 on the establishment of the "Protector of Nature" badge;

The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated August 18, 2022 "On measures to further improve the activities of the Research Institute of Environment and Nature Protection Technologies";

Resolution No. 530 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the establishment of the state reserve "Borsakelmas" in the Republic of Karakalpakstan" (September 27, 2022);

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 666 (November 23, 2022) "On improving the procedure for calculating damage caused to natural objects during illegal extraction of materials in Noru";

With the participation of the United Nations Development Program and the Global Ecological Fund of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Lakes, wetlands and coastal areas as a basis for supporting sustainable life in the degraded lands of the Aral Sea basin landscape" Resolution No. 686 (November 30, 2022) on measures to implement the project of "preservation and management of the territories";

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-269 of December 21, 2022 "On measures to implement administrative reforms of the new Uzbekistan".[2]

"Uzbekistan-2030" strategy was developed taking into account the current problems and shortcomings, problems and shortcomings that may arise in the future. In this regard, the Honorable President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev signed the Decree "On Strategy of Actions" on September 11, 2023. To become one of the countries with higher than average income through sustainable economic growth, to organize an education, medical and social protection system that fully meets the requirements of the population and international standards, to create favorable environmental conditions for the population, 5 priorities and 100 goals are reflected in the "Uzbekistan-2030" action strategy, which provides for the establishment of a fair and modern state in the service of the people, guaranteeing the sovereignty and security of the country. In particular, the third priority area is devoted to the conservation of water resources and environmental protection and includes the following goals:

Fundamental improvement of the ecological situation in the republic, elimination of environmental problems affecting human life;

Expansion of the nationwide project "Green Space" aimed at stabilizing the ecological situation;

Expanding the area of forests;

Stabilizing the ecological situation in the Aral Sea region, mitigating the negative effects of environmental problems caused by the drying up of the Aral Sea;

Prevention of negative effects of climate change;

Ensuring reliable preservation of biological diversity;

Improving the quality of solid household waste collection and removal services;

Taking drastic measures to prevent atmospheric air pollution and preserve its natural composition.[3]

In Samarkand, the executive secretary of the UN Convention to Combat Desertification and Drought, Ibrahim Tiav, and the Minister of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change, Aziz Abduhakimov, signed an agreement on holding the 21st session of the Committee to Review the Implementation of the Convention to Combat Desertification (CRIC-21).[4]

Under the chairmanship of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, on October 11, a video selector meeting was held on the issues of fully utilizing the potential of tourism and cultural centers, organizing the autumn season of the nationwide project "Green Space". The works within the national project "Green Space" were also thoroughly reviewed.

It has been 2 years since this movement started in our country. During this period, more than 1,200 hectares of green gardens and public parks, more than 1 million hectares of green areas and pavements were built. In general, the attitude towards the tree has changed in the society and in the authorities.

Now, from October 25 to December 1, the "autumn tree planting season" is announced. 85 million saplings are planned to be planted this season.

For this purpose, the Republican headquarters will be formed, and the heads of the Academy of Sciences, Institutes of Soil Science and Forestry, and forestry will be included in it. They determine the type of seedlings based on soil analysis and climatic conditions.

200 saplings will be delivered to each neighborhood free of charge by the Forestry Agency. Also, from October 15, a seedling fair will be organized in all districts and neighborhoods.[5]

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

So, loving one's motherland, honoring and longing for all that it has is a delicate feeling that exists in human nature. No matter where he goes, he still sands his homeland. Because when a person sees the face of the world, he first begins to breathe the air of his homeland, learns to take his first steps in the soil of his homeland, and begins to know the world by understanding this homeland. Protecting the soil where the first umbilical cord blood was spilled and where the first steps were taken is our human duty to the Motherland. As our president said: "Those who say that the preservation and protection of peace and tranquility are the duty of only the employees of certain fields are very wrong." In this way, all of us, the whole nation, should be more united and act in solidarity. There is a lot of wisdom in the saying "take care of your own house" and its meaning is broad. After all, it is necessary to fight for peace, no one will create it".

Representatives of each field should contribute within their field to protect the peace of the country. For example, if teachers explain to students that the unity of the motherland and the protection of the motherland is a sacred duty, the young generation will grow up with a sense of loyalty to the motherland. As a result, our future generations will feel from the heart how great our task is to protect the country, and they will be determined to do so they grow up to be patriots. One of the thinkers said: "A patriot is a person who, because of his love for his people, does not spare his wealth, energy, and life, and sacrifices everything for the freedom and well-being of his people and his country".

DISCUSSION

The world is facing many environmental problems day by day. These problems include: global warming, acid rain, air pollution and water pollution. People are the biggest cause of these problems. On February 2, 2022, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev expressed these thoughts in his speech on improving the environmental culture of the population at the meeting of video selectors regarding the priority tasks in 2022 regarding the improvement of the waste management system and the improvement of the ecological situation in the regions, the implementation of the nationwide project "Green Space" passed:

"You all know very well that our people have long regarded nature as sacred. He tried to keep the soil, water, air and threshold clean. In our people, the wise saying "If you cut one, plant ten" is not for nothing.

When a new child is born in the family, a sapling is planted for him. Unfortunately, these good habits have almost disappeared today.

In order for our generations to live in a decent natural environment after us, we should pay attention to nature and live in harmony with it.

What does it mean? This means keeping nature clean, protecting land and water resources, the ecological system, planting trees and creating gardens.

The most important issue is that we should seriously focus on increasing the ecological culture of the population." [6]

PROPOSAL

Strengthen legal measures for environmental damage and introduce more serious penalties for administrative and criminal liability, and ensure their implementation. It is also necessary to organize various activities to strengthen environmental control and public control, to increase the environmental culture of citizens. It is necessary to expand the "Green Space" project and develop similar projects, and involve the general public in the process of their implementation. In order to increase the ecological culture of the population, organization of contests such as "Exemplary Family", "Most Prosperous Neighborhood" and "Environmental Knowledge", organizing monthly monitoring under the slogan "Connection with Nature".

CONCLUSION

It is difficult to imagine the country without the people. The most important and most important thing in the achievement of independence of our country is that our people showed to the whole world their patience, wisdom, tolerance, virtue of hard work and creativity, and that they are able to go towards the set goal with determination, relying first of all on their own strength and potential. In instilling patriotism in young people, it is necessary to rely on immortal values such as spirituality, morals, and enlightenment. These three great values have been cherished by our people for centuries. Both our holy religion and the entire Eastern philosophy share these values glorified, considered them to be the most important conditions of social development.

We are loyal children to the Motherland only if we deeply understand these ideas and values, and most importantly, if we can demonstrate them in our practical actions and the motherland is as dear and lonely as a mother. She is our first and last word.

Since the creation of humanity, its life has been closely connected with nature. Every day we take advantage of the blessings He has given us and grow in His bosom. While our ancestors achieved great results in the path of science, they thought about leaving a worthy legacy to the generations. Their scientific achievements continue to amaze the people of the world. So, what is our heritage? How will our descendants remember us? Is there a greater legacy than a prosperous, free, prosperous Motherland! So! Our greatest wealth is the Motherland. Every part of it, every drop of its water, every particle of its soil is a deposit for us, it is our human duty to protect them.

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